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A BOOK REVIEW ON 'BLUE OCEAN STRATEGY'

Mrs. Divya Prabhu P.

Research Scholar in Management at Jain University, Bangalore
Asst. Professor, Dept. of Business Administration,
Sahyadri College of Engineering & Management, Mangalore

Abstract:

The book that I have reviewed is "Blue Ocean Strategy". Now you might ask me what's so special about a Blue Ocean. Aren't all oceans blue? And how can you possibly have a strategy called Blue Ocean Strategy? What has oceans got to do with strategy? Well, you have to read it to understand it!!

"Blue Ocean Strategy" authored by W. Chan Kim and Renie Maugborgne is an international best seller. The authors are the founders of the Value Innovation Network (VIN), a global community of practice on the Value Innovation Family of concepts and also board members of the Value Innovation Action Tank (VIAT) in Singapore.

The authors say that this is a book about friendship, about loyalty; about believing in one another, because of which they set out to explore the ideas in this book and eventually came to write it. This book is the victory of friendship between a professor and a student that they have found more meaningful than any idea in the world of business. The authors, right in the beginning, say that this book is not meant for those whose ambition in life is to get by or merely to survive, but for those who want to make a difference i.e. to create a company that builds a future where customers, employees, shareholders and society win. Building a company is not an easy task, but it is possible if you make smart strategic moves. Creation of Blue Ocean Strategy is one among such moves.

Key words: Blue Ocean Strategy, smart strategic moves, Value Innovation.

Introduction:

Blue Ocean Strategy challenges companies to break out of the red ocean of bloody competition by creating UNCONTESTED MARKET SPACE that makes the competition IRRELEVANT. Instead of dividing up existing demand and benchmarking competitors, Blue Ocean Strategy is about growing demand and breaking away from the competitions. This book not only challenges companies, but also shows them how to achieve this.

The authors have given an excellent introduction to a set of analytical tools and frameworks that shows you how to systematically act on this challenge. They have also elaborated the principles that define and separate Blue Ocean Strategy from competition based strategic thought.

A market universe is composed of two sorts of oceans: Red Ocean and Blue Ocean. Red Ocean represents all the industries in existence today. This is the 'Known market space'. Blue Ocean denotes all the industries not in existence today. This is the 'Unknown Market Space'.

In the Red Oceans, industry boundaries are defined and accepted and the competitive rules of the game are known. Here the companies try to outperform their rivals to grab a greater share of existing demand. As the market space gets crowded, scope for profits and growth is reduced. Products become commodities and cut throat competition turns ocean red and bloody.

Blue Ocean in contrast is defined by untapped market space, demand creation and the opportunity for highly profitable growth. Although some blue oceans are created well beyond existing industry boundaries, most are created from within red oceans by expanding existing industry boundaries. In Blue oceans, competition is irrelevant because the rules of the game are waiting to be set.

The author agrees that red oceans will always be a fact of business life until there is existence of competition, but competing for a share of contracting markets is insufficient to sustain high performance when supply exceeds demand. Companies must go beyond competition. To earn new profit and growth opportunity, they need to create Blue Ocean.

In this book you get little practical guidance on how to create them. This book provides practical frameworks and analytics for the systematic pursuit and capture of blue oceans.

The term 'blue oceans' is new, their existence is not. They are a feature of past as well as present business life. If we look back one hundred years, we note that as many industries such as automobile, aviation, management consulting that are flourishing today were unknown at that time. If we make note of industries like biotechnology, cell phones, mutual funds, etc none of these existed in a meaningful way just three decades ago. Now put the clock forward twenty years and ask yourself how many unknown industries will likely exist then. If history is any predictor of future, again answer is many of them. The reality is that industries never stand still. They continuously evolve, operations improve, markets expand and players come and go. History teaches us that we have a hugely underestimated capacity to create new industries and re-create existing ones.

Value Innovation: The Corner stone of Blue Ocean Strategy:

Value innovation is the corner stone of Blue Ocean Strategy. It is called value innovation because instead of focusing on beating the competition, you focus on making the competition irrelevant by creating a leap in the value of buyers and your company thereby opening up new and uncontested market space.

Value innovation is a new way of thinking about and executing strategy that results in the creation of a blue ocean and a break from the competition. It is conventionally believed that companies can either create greater value to customers at a higher cost or create reasonable value at a lower cost. But those that seek to create blue oceans pursue differentiation and low cost simultaneously.

The issue now is how to succeed in blue oceans. How can companies systematically maximize the opportunities, while simultaneously minimizing the risks of formulating and executing Blue Ocean Strategy? If you lack an understanding of the opportunity maximizing and risk minimizing principles driving the creation and capture of blue oceans, the odds will be lengthened against your blue ocean initiative.

Strategy will always involve both opportunity and risk, be it a red ocean or a blue ocean initiative. But at present, the playing field is dramatically unbalanced in favor of tools and analytical framework to succeed in Red Ocean. As long as this remains true, red oceans will continue to dominate companies' strategic agenda.

This book seeks to address this imbalance by laying out a methodology to support the authors' thesis. Here the author has presented the principles and analytical frameworks to succeed in blue oceans.

Let me give you a bird's eye view of the contents of this international best seller.

There are 9 chapters explaining the readers on different aspects relating to Blue Ocean Strategy. They include,

- A brief introduction of Blue Ocean Strategy.
- The analytical tools and frameworks that are essential for creating and capturing Blue Oceans
- The paths to create uncontested market space across diverse industry domains.
- Designing company's strategic planning process to go beyond incremental improvements

This book also explains how to maximize the size of Blue Ocean and also to understand the universe of non-customers.

Here we come to learning of a very interesting topic. Something related to the categorizing of NON CUSTOMERS!! There are three tiers of non customers who can be transformed into customers.

The first tier of non customers is closest to your markets who sit on the edge. They are mentally non customers and are buyers who purchase your offer out of necessity. If such buyers are offered a leap in the value, their purchase would multiply unlocking latent demand. The second tier of non customers is those who refuse to use your industry's offerings. They have seen your offers as an option to fulfill their needs but have voted against them. The third tier of non customers is farthest from your market. They have never thought of your market offerings as an option.

The author has explained how to deal with these tiers of non customers, how to attract them and expand your blue ocean.

- It also includes the integration of execution into strategy making which motivates the people to act on a blue ocean strategy.
- Then, the dynamic aspects of blue ocean strategy, the issues of sustainability and renewal are also discussed in the end.

The principles proposed in this book would serve as important pointers for every company which is thinking about its future strategy. But please do remember that this is not to suggest that companies will suddenly stop competing. On the contrary, the competition will be more present and will surely remain a critical factor of the market reality. What the authors suggest is that to obtain high performance in this overcrowded market, companies should go beyond competing.

Blue and Red Ocean have always co existed. But companies need to succeed in both oceans and master the strategies for both. The companies need to learn how to make the competition irrelevant. This book aims to help balance the scales so that formulating and executing blue oceans strategy can become as systematic and actionable as competing in the red ocean of known market space.

The essence of Blue Ocean Strategy is made clear by quoting examples of strategies adopted by business leaders like Henry Ford, Hollerith, Thomas Watson, Stan Durwood etc., which indeed contributed to strong profitable growth of their organization. Here are a few examples.

The authors have explained about the paths of creating uncontested market space. One among them is the path of looking across the chain of buyers.

An industry typically converges on a single buyer group. For example, Pharmaceutical industry focuses on doctors, isn't it?

Challenging an industry's conventional wisdom about- 'which buyer group to target' can lead to the discovery of new Blue Ocean. Let the industries look across the buyer's groups where they can gain new insights.

Think of Novo Nordisk, the Danish insulin producer that created a blue ocean in the insulin industry. Insulin is one, which is prescribed by the doctors to the diabetic patients to regulate the level of sugar in their blood. Naturally, the doctors were their target group for any insulin industry. However, little progress could be made in that direction. Competition was rapidly occurring among the major players. Now, Nordisk saw that it could break away from the competition and create a blue ocean by shifting the industry's long standing focus on the doctors to the users i.e the patients themselves!! The problem here was the difficulty in injecting it by the patients which was supplied to them in vials. This was highly difficult task on the part of the patients to handle the syringes, needles, insulin etc. this created unpleasant feelings for the patients. This led NovoNordisk to the blue ocean opportunity of NovoPen, launched in the year 1985. It was the first user-friendly insulin delivery solution to remove the hassle and embarrassment of administering insulin. It looked just like a fountain pen. It was easy to handle, easy to carry which helped even the blind patients use it properly. In this way, after creating the blue ocean that the Nordisk unlocked, they further succeeded in dominating the blue ocean by introducing further developments and new innovations in their industry. Thus blue ocean strategy enabled the Nordisk to shift the industry landscape and transform their company from a mere insulin producer to a diabetes care company.

Here is one more example, which shows how you have to look across complementary product and service offerings.

In most industries, rivals converge within the bounds of their industry's product and service offerings. Take movie theatres. The ease and cost of getting a baby-sitter and parking car affect the perceived value of going to the movies. You may be thinking what have movie theatres got to do with babysitting services? But in reality, this complementary service definitely affects the demand for the business of movie theatres. These services are beyond the bounds of the movie theatre industry. Yet, imagine a movie theatre with a baby-sitting service and we may note that the untapped value is hidden in the complementary products and services. The key is to anticipate what the buyers expect when they choose a product or service. A simple way to do so is to think about what happens before, during and after your product is used. In the above case, baby-sitting and car parking facility is needed before people can go to the movies, isn't it? Here the industry is trying to move away from COMPETITION. This is the essence of Blue Ocean Strategy.

Now let's turn to the computer industry. In the mid 1990s, Dell Computer Corporation created a Blue Ocean in the computer industry. Traditionally, computer manufacturers competed on offering faster computers having more features and software. Dell challenged this industry logic. Guess what they did?

Perhaps readers would have witnessed how Dell changed the purchasing and delivery experiences of buyers. Dell introduced direct sales to customers. It further appealed to customers because Dell offered unprecedented delivery time. For examples, the time it took from order to customer-delivery was just four days, when compared with its competitor's average. Moreover, through Dell's online and telephone ordering system, customers were given the options to customize their machines to their liking. Today, as a result, the Dell is the undisputed market leader in PC sales.

Coming back to the theatre industry, it was set on a new profitable growth trajectory through the creation of a new blue ocean. In 1963, Stan Durwood undertook a strategic move that turned the industry on its head. Stan Durwood revitalized the Movie Theatre that was opened by his father, with the creation of the first Multiplex in a Kansas City Shopping Centre. The Multiplex was an instant hit (a cinema with several screens, which is now commonly seen in cities). The multiplex gave the viewers a greater choice. With different sized theatres in one place, the owners could make adjustments to meet varying demands for movies thereby spreading the risk and keeping the costs down. As a result, Durwood's company, AMC i.e. American Multi-Cinema, became the second largest Movie Company in the nation, as the blue ocean of multiplex spread across America.

To conclude, Blue ocean opportunities have been out there. As they have been explored, the market universe has been expanding. This expansion is believed to be the root of growth. Yet the poor understanding exists both in theory and in practice as to how to systematically create and capture Blue oceans. The authors invite you to read this book to learn how you can be a driver of this expansion in the future.

If you are an ambitious person who wants to make it big in life, whether you have the genes to make big in business or in the corporate world, this book is a must for you!! ☺